

Exterior set in Neutrosophic biminimal structure spaces

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Abstract: We start with studying the concept of some fundamental properties of exterior set in neutrosophic biminimal structure space.

Key words: minimal structure spaces, neutrosophic biminimal structure spaces, exterior set in neutrosophic biminimal structure space

1. Introduction

The contribution of mathematics to the present-day technology in reaching to a fast trend cannot be ignored. The theories presented differently from classical methods in studies such as fuzzy set [24], intuitionistic fuzzy sets [4], intuitionistic set [6], neutrosophic set [23], etc., have great importance in this contribution of mathematics in recent years. Many works have been done on these sets by mathematicians in many areas of mathematics [1–3, 5, 7–16, 18]. The idea of minimal structure (in short, m-structure) was introduced by V. Popa and T. Noiri [19] in 2000. The notion of neutrosophic biminimal structure space (in short, nbiss) was introduced by S. Ganesan and C. Alexander [17] in 2021. Also they introduced and studied $N_{mX}^1 N_{mX}^2$ -closed sets and $N_{mX}^1 N_{mX}^2$ -open sets in nbiss and, also the application of index number (Statistical theory) is inspired from the concept of nbiss in real world. In this work, we introduced the concept of exterior set in nbiss and studied some of their basic properties.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [17] Let H be a nonempty set & N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2 be nms on H . A triple (H, N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2) is said to be nbiss.

Definition 2.2. [17] Let (H, N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2) be a nbiss and E be any neutrosophic set. Then

1. Every $E \in N_{mH}^j$ is open & its complement is closed, respectively, for $j = 1, 2$.
2. $N_m cl_j$ -closure of $E = \text{minimum } \{U : U \text{ is } N_{mH}^j\text{-closed set and } U \geq E\}$, respectively, for $j = 1, 2$ and it is denoted by $N_m cl_j(E)$.

3. $N_{mH} \text{int}_j$ -interior of E = maximum $\{W : W \text{ is } N_{mH}^j\text{-open set and } W \leq E\}$, respectively, for $j = 1, 2$ and it is denoted by $N_{mH} \text{int}_j(E)$.

Definition 2.3. [17] A subset E of a nbiss (H, N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2) is said to be $N_{mH}^1 N_{mH}^2$ -closed if $N_{mH} \text{cl}_1(N_{mH} \text{cl}_2(E)) = E$.

Definition 2.4. [17] Let (H, N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2) be a nbiss and E be a subset of H . Then E is $N_{mH}^1 N_{mH}^2$ -closed iff $N_{mH} \text{cl}_1(E) = E$ and $N_{mH} \text{cl}_2(E) = E$.

Proposition 2.1. [17] Let (H, N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2) be a nbiss. If E and F are $N_{mH}^1 N_{mH}^2$ -closed subsets of (H, N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2) , then $E \wedge F$ is $N_{mH}^1 N_{mH}^2$ -closed.

Proposition 2.2. [17] Let (H, N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2) be a nbiss. Then E is a $N_{mH}^1 N_{mH}^2$ -open subset of (H, N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2) if and only if $E = N_{mH} \text{int}_1(N_{mH} \text{int}_2(E))$.

3. $N_{mH}^i N_{mH}^j$ -EXTERIOR

Definition 3.1. Let (H, N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2) be a nbiss, E a subset of H and $h \in H$. We called h to be the $N_{mH}^i N_{mH}^j$ -exterior point of E if $h \in N_{mH} \text{int}_i(N_{mH} \text{int}_j(H \setminus E))$. We denote the set of all $N_{mH}^i N_{mH}^j$ -exterior points of E by $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E)$ where $i, j = 1, 2$ and $i \neq j$.

From definition we have $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E) = H \setminus N_{mH} \text{cl}_i(N_{mH} \text{cl}_j(E))$.

Example 3.1. Let $H = \{h\}$ with $N_{mH}^1 = \{0_\sim, A, 1_\sim\}$; $(N_{mH}^1)^C = \{1_\sim, B, 0_\sim\}$ and

$N_{mH}^2 = \{0_\sim, U, 1_\sim\}$; $(N_{mH}^2)^C = \{1_\sim, V, 0_\sim\}$ where

$A = \prec (0.9, 0.3, 0.8) \succ$; $B = \prec (0.8, 0.7, 0.9) \succ$

$U = \prec (0.5, 0.5, 0.7) \succ$; $V = \prec (0.7, 0.5, 0.5) \succ$

WKT $0_\sim = \{\prec h, 0, 0, 1 \succ : h \in H\}$, $1_\sim = \{\prec h, 1, 1, 0 \succ : h \in H\}$ and $0_\sim^C = \{\prec h, 1, 1, 0 \succ : h \in H\}$, $1_\sim^C = \{\prec h, 0, 0, 1 \succ : h \in H\}$.

Now we define $G = \prec (0.3, 0.4, 0.5) \succ$.

Then $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(\prec (0.3, 0.4, 0.5) \succ) = H \setminus N_{mH} \text{cl}_i(N_{mH} \text{cl}_j(\prec (0.3, 0.4, 0.5) \succ))$. Hence $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{12}(\prec (0.3, 0.4, 0.5) \succ) = H \setminus N_{mH} \text{cl}_1(N_{mH} \text{cl}_2(\prec (0.3, 0.4, 0.5) \succ)) = 0_\sim$.

Lemma 3.1. Let (H, N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2) be a nbiss and E be a subset of H . Then for each $i, j = 1, 2$ & $i \neq j$, we have;

1. $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E) \cap E = 0_\sim$.
2. $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(0_\sim) = 1_\sim$.
3. $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(1_\sim) = 0_\sim$.

Proof. (1) Since $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E) = H \setminus N_{mH} \text{cl}_i(N_{mH} \text{cl}_j(E))$ and $E \subset N_{mH} \text{cl}_i(N_{mH} \text{cl}_j(E))$, $(H \setminus N_{mH} \text{cl}_i(N_{mH} \text{cl}_j(E))) \cap E \subseteq (H \setminus E) \cap E = 0_\sim$. Therefore $(H \setminus N_{mH} \text{cl}_i(N_{mH} \text{cl}_j(E))) \cap E = 0_\sim$. Hence $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E) \cap E = 0_\sim$.

(2) $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(0_\sim) = 1_\sim \setminus N_{mH} \text{cl}_i(N_{mH} \text{cl}_j(0_\sim)) = 1_\sim \setminus 0_\sim = 1_\sim$.

(3) $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(1_\sim) = 1_\sim \setminus N_{mH} \text{cl}_i(N_{mH} \text{cl}_j(1_\sim)) = 1_\sim \setminus 1_\sim = 0_\sim$. □

Theorem 3.1. *Let (H, N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2) be a nbiss and E, F be a subset of H . If $E \subseteq F$, then $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(F) \subseteq N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E)$ where $i, j = 1, 2$ & $i \neq j$.*

Proof. Assume that (H, N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2) is a nbiss, E, F are subset of H and $E \subseteq F$. Thus $N_{mcl_i}(N_{mcl_j}(E)) \subseteq N_{mcl_i}(N_{mcl_j}(F))$ and $H \setminus N_{mcl_i}(N_{mcl_j}(F)) \subseteq H \setminus N_{mcl_i}(N_{mcl_j}(E))$. Hence $N_{mX} \text{Ext}_{ij}(F) \subseteq N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E)$ for each $i, j = 1, 2$ and $i \neq j$. \square

Theorem 3.2. *Let (H, N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2) be a nbiss and E a subset of H . Then for each $i, j = 1, 2$ and $i \neq j$, E is $N_{mH}^i N_{mH}^j$ -closed if and only if $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E) = H \setminus E$.*

Proof. (1) \Rightarrow (2) Let E be a subset of H . Assume that E is $N_{mH}^i N_{mH}^j$ -closed. Thus $E = mcl_i(N_{mcl_j}(E))$. Therefore $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E) = H \setminus mcl_i(N_{mcl_j}(E)) = H \setminus E$.

(2) \Rightarrow (1) Assume that $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E) = H \setminus E$. Thus $H \setminus mcl_i(N_{mcl_j}(E)) = H \setminus E$. Consequently $mcl_i(N_{mcl_j}(E)) = E$ and E is $N_{mH}^i N_{mH}^j$ -closed. \square

Corollary 3.1. *Let (H, N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2) be a nbiss and E a subset of H . Then for each $i, j = 1, 2$ & $i \neq j$, E is $N_{mH}^i N_{mH}^j$ -open if and only if $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(H \setminus E) = E$.*

Proof. (1) \Rightarrow (2) Let E be a subset of H . Assume that E is $N_{mH}^i N_{mH}^j$ -open. Thus $H \setminus E$ is $N_{mH}^i N_{mH}^j$ -closed. Therefore $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(H \setminus E) = H \setminus (H \setminus E) = E$.

(2) \Rightarrow (1) Assume that $N_{mX} \text{Ext}_{ij}(H \setminus E) = E$. Thus $E = N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(H \setminus E) = H \setminus mcl_i(N_{mcl_j}(H \setminus E)) = N_{mint_i}(N_{mint_j}(E))$. Hence E is $N_{mH}^i N_{mH}^j$ -open. \square

Theorem 3.3. *Let (H, N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2) be a nbiss and E be a subset of H . If E is $N_{mH}^i N_{mH}^j$ -closed, then $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(H \setminus N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E)) = N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E)$, where $i, j = 1, 2$ & $i \neq j$.*

Proof. Assume that E is $N_{mH}^i N_{mH}^j$ -closed. Thus $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E) = H \setminus E$. Hence $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(H \setminus N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E)) = N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(H \setminus (H \setminus E)) = N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E)$. \square

Theorem 3.4. *Let (H, N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2) be a nbiss and E, F be subsets of H . Then for each $i, j = 1, 2$ & $i \neq j$, we have;*

1. $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E) \cup N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(F) \subseteq N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E \cap F)$.
2. If E and F are $N_{mH}^i N_{mH}^j$ -closed, then $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E) \cup N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(F) = N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E \cap F)$.

Proof. Assume that (H, N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2) is a nbiss, E and F are subsets of H . (1). Since $E \cap F \subseteq E$ and $E \cap F \subseteq F$, we have $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E) \subseteq N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E \cap F)$ and $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(F) \subseteq N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E \cap F)$. It follows that $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E) \cup N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(F) \subseteq N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E \cap F)$.

(2). Assume that E and F are $N_{mH}^i N_{mH}^j$ -closed. Then $E \cap F$ is $N_{mH}^i N_{mH}^j$ -closed. Thus $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E \cap F) = H \setminus (E \cap F) = (H \setminus E) \cup (H \setminus F) = N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E) \cup N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(F)$. \square

Theorem 3.5. *Let (H, N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2) be a nbiss and E, F be subsets of H . Then for each $i, j = 1, 2$ & $i \neq j$, we have;*

1. $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E \cup F) \subseteq N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E) \cap N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(F)$.
2. If E and F are $N_{mH}^i N_{mH}^j$ -open, then $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E \cup F) = N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E) \cap N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(F)$.

Proof. Assume that (H, N_{mH}^1, N_{mH}^2) is a nbiss, E and F are subsets of H . (1). Since $E \subseteq E \cup F$ and $F \subseteq E \cup F$, we have $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E \cup F) \subseteq N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E)$ and $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E \cup F) \subseteq N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(F)$. It follows that $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E \cup F) \subseteq N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(E) \cap N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(F)$.

(2). Assume that E and F are $N_{mH}^i N_{mH}^j$ -open. Then $E \cup F$ is $N_{mH}^i N_{mH}^j$ -open. It follows that $H \setminus E$, $H \setminus F$ and $H \setminus (E \cup F)$ are $N_{mH}^i N_{mH}^j$ -closed. Thus by Theorem 3.4(2), we have $N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(H \setminus E) \cup N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(H \setminus F) = N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}((H \setminus E) \cap (H \setminus F)) = N_{mH} \text{Ext}_{ij}(H \setminus (E \cup F)) = E \cup F$. \square

Conclusion

We presented several new notions and related properties by utilizing the concept of exterior set in nbiss.

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References

- [1] M. Abdel-Basset, A. Gamal, L. H. Son and F. Smarandache, A bipolar neutrosophic multi criteria decision Making frame work for professional selection. *Appl. Sci*, (2020), 10, (1202), 1-22.
- [2] M. Abdel-Basset, R. Mohamed, A. E. N. H. Zaided, A. Gamal and F. Smarandache, Solving the supply chain problem using the best-worst method based on a novel plithogenic model. In *Optimization Theory Based on Neutrosophic and Plithogenic Sets*, (2020), (pp. 1-19). Academic Press.
- [3] I. Arokiarani, R. Dhavaseelan, S. Jafari and M. Parimala1, On some new notions and functions in neutrosophic topological spaces, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, (2017), 16, 16-19.
- [4] K. T. Atanassov, Intuitionistic fuzzy sets. *Fuzzy sets and systems*, (1986), 20, 87-96.
- [5] M. Caldas, R. Dhavaseelan, M. Ganster and S. Jafari, Neutrosophic resolvable and neutrosophic irresolvable spaces, *New Trends in Neutrosophic Theory and Applications. Volume II*, (2018), 328-336.
- [6] D. Coker, A note on intuitionistic sets and intuitionistic points, *Turkish Journal of Mathematics*, 20(3),(1996), 343-351.
- [7] R. Dhavaseelan and S. Jafari, Generalized neutrosophic closed sets, *New Trends in Neutrosophic Theory and Applications. Volume II*, (2018), 245-258
- [8] R. Dhavaseelan, M. Ganster, S. Jafari and M. Parimala, On neutrosophic α -supra open sets and neutrosophic α -supra continuous functions, *New Trends in Neutrosophic Theory and Applications. Volume II*, (2018), 273-282
- [9] R. Dhavaseelan, S. Jafari, C. Özel and M. A. Al-Shumrani, Generalized neutrosophic contra-continuity, *New Trends in Neutrosophic Theory and Applications. Volume II*, (2018), 283-298
- [10] R. Dhavaseelan, S. Jafari, R. M. Latif and F. Smarandache, Neutrosophic rare α -continuity, *New Trends in Neutrosophic Theory and Applications. Volume II*, (2018), 337-345
- [11] R. Dhavaseelan1, S. Jafari, N. Rajesh, F. Smarandache, Neutrosophic semi-continuous multifunctions, *New Trends in Neutrosophic Theory and Applications. Volume II*, (2018), 346-355
- [12] S. Ganesan and F. Smarandache, Some new classes of neutrosophic minimal open sets, *Asia Mathematika*, 5(1), (2021), 103-112. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4724804.

- [13] S. Ganesan, C. Alexander, A. Pandi and F. Smarandache, Neutrosophic micro ideal topological structure, *International Journal of Mathematics And its Applications*, 9(2), (2021), 127-136.
- [14] S. Ganesan, Neutrosophic grill topological spaces, *International Research Journal of Education and Technology*, 2(2), June (2021), 01-16.
- [15] S. Ganesan and F. Smarandache, Neutrosophic biminimal α -open sets, *Bulletin of the International Mathematical Virtual Institute*, 11(3), (2021), 545-553.
- [16] S. Ganesan, C. Alexander and F. Smarandache, On N_m - α -open sets in neutrosophic minimal structure spaces, *Journal of Mathematics and Computational Intelligence*, 1(1)(2021), 23-32.
- [17] S. Ganesan and C. Alexander, Neutrosophic biminimal structure spaces, *Journal of Mathematics and Computational Intelligence*, 1(1)(2021), 67-74.
- [18] M. Parimala, M. Karthika, R. Dhavaseelan, S. Jafari, On neutrosophic supra pre-Continuous functions in neutrosophic topological spaces, *New Trends in Neutrosophic Theory and Applications. Volume II*, (2018), 356-368
- [19] V. Popa and T. Noiri, On \mathcal{M} -continuous functions. *Anal. Univ. Dunarea de Jos Galati. Ser. Mat. Fiz. Mec. Teor. Fasc. II*, (2000), 18 (23), 31-41.
- [20] A. A. Salama and S. A. Alblawi, Neutrosophic Set and Neutrosophic Topological Spaces. *IOSR J. Math*, (2012), 3, 31-35.
- [21] F. Smarandache and G. Savoiu, Neutrosophic index number : Neutrosophic logic applied in the statistical indicators theory. *Critical Review ; A publication of Society for Mathematics of Uncertainty*, Volume XI, (2015), 67-100.
- [22] F. Smarandache, Neutrosophy and Neutrosophic Logic. *First International Conference on Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Logic Set, Probability and Statistics*, University of New Mexico, Gallup, NM, USA, (2002).
- [23] F. Smarandache, *A Unifying Field in Logics: Neutrosophic Logic. Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Set, Neutrosophic Probability*. American Research Press: Rehoboth, NM, USA, (1999).
- [24] L. A. Zadeh, Fuzzy Sets. *Information and Control*, (1965), 18, 338-353.